

Ni-Catalyzed Reductive Dicarbofunctionalization of Non-activated Alkenes: Scope and Mechanistic Insights

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ABSTRACT: Olefins devoid of directing or activating groups have been dicarbofunctionalized here with two electrophilic carbon sources under reductive conditions. Simultaneous formation of one C(sp³)-C(sp³) and one C(sp³)-C(sp²) bond across a variety of unbiased π -systems proceeds with exquisite selectivity by the combination of a Ni catalyst with TDAE as sacrificial reductant. Control experiments and computational studies revealed the feasibility of a radical-based mechanism involving, formally, two interconnected Ni(I)/Ni(III) processes and demonstrated the different ability of Ni(I) species (Ni(I)I vs PhNi(I)) to reduce the C(sp³)-I bond. The role of the reductant was also investigated in depth, suggesting that a one-electron reduction of Ni(II) species to Ni(I) is thermodynamically favored. Further, the preferential activation of alkyl vs aryl halides by ArNi(I) complexes as well as the high affinity of ArNi(II) for secondary over tertiary C-centered radicals explains the lack of undesired homo- and direct coupling products (Ar-Ar, Ar-Alk) in these transformations.

Olefins are ubiquitous motifs in natural products and pharmaceuticals, serving as one of the most common templates for the chemo-, regio-, and stereoselective incorporation of C-C and C-X bonds in organic molecules. Alkenes also represent an excellent platform for the late-stage edition of complex organic molecules due to their orthogonal reactivity with respect to carbonyls and other polar functional groups.¹ The difunctionalization of alkenes represents one of the most efficient strategies to install two vicinal chemical bonds in a step- and operation-economic fashion. In particular, intermolecular three-component dicarbofunctionalization reactions have attracted significant attention in recent years because of their convergence toward the simultaneous construction of two C-C bonds and hence their ability to access more complex aliphatic structures in a rapid manner.² While metal-free protocols have been developed in this context,³ reactions catalyzed by transition metals have been shown to be more generally applicable. Thus, palladium catalysis has been successfully used in the vicinal dicarbofunctionalization of conjugated dienes as well as of olefins bearing a directing group.^{4,5} Despite the profound impact of these transformations, multiple limitations still remain unsolved. First, the lack of reactivity of unactivated olefins or olefins lacking a directing

group or a vicinal double bond to stabilize the corresponding alkyl-Pd intermediates. Second, only C(sp²)-groups could be incorporated across the π -system. Some of these limitations have been overcome by the use of first row transition metals. Representative examples can be found with iron and copper regarding the carboarylation of styrenes using α -bromoester derivatives and trifluoromethylating reagents, respectively.^{6,7} However, nickel complexes have played a more prominent role in this context, as they were able to promote the dicarbofunctionalization of alkenes incorporating alkyl groups.⁸ Still, only olefins containing directing groups or electronically biased substrates (i.e., activated olefins bearing electron-withdrawing groups) are amenable to this set of reaction conditions. Furthermore, in most of the above-mentioned cases, highly reactive and thus sensitive organo-metallic species such as organozinc or Grignard reagents are needed for a successful outcome (Scheme 1a). It is important to note that these organometallic species are typically prepared from the corresponding organic halides.⁹ Thus, the ability to promote a catalytic dicarbofunctionalizations that would directly involve the corresponding halides as reaction partners would be highly desirable. The advantages of such approach would primarily stem from the ready avail-

ability of these species, which could avoid the use of stoichiometric and highly reactive organometallic reagents, thus increasing the overall functional group compatibility. In addition, these processes would also profit from a high operational simplicity, sustainability, and cost-efficiency.¹⁰ While conceptually interesting, the inherent low reactivity of electrophiles and their proclivity towards undesired pathways (homocoupling, β -hydride elimination) constitute serious challenges that need to be overcome.¹¹

Previous work: Dicarbofunctionalizations of directed, activated alkenes:

■ a. Redox Neutral and Oxidative Dicarbofunctionalizations

■ b. Reductive Dicarbofunctionalization (refs. 14, 15)

Limitations: NO reactivity on unbiased alkenes

This work: Reductive dicarbofunctionalizations of unactivated alkenes

Scheme 1. Metal-catalyzed dicarbofunctionalization of alkenes.

Over the past decade, reductive couplings involving two electrophiles, have evolved into a powerful alternative to forge carbon-carbon bonds, in most cases catalyzed by nickel complexes.^{12,13} Inspired by the advantages of reductive cross-coupling approaches, our group recently developed a nickel-catalyzed intermolecular reductive alkylarylation of alkenes.¹⁴ This three-component reaction utilized alkyl and aryl iodides in the presence of TDAE as stoichiometric reductant to dicarbofunctionalize, in a regio- and stereoselective fashion, electronically biased olefins as well as allylic systems bearing weak coordinating groups (Scheme 1b). Our protocol, devoid of organometallic species, not only offered broad functional group compatibility due to the mild reaction conditions but also broadened the

scope in the olefinic partners compared to previous reports.⁸

Despite these advances, unactivated olefins or alkenes lacking a directing/coordinating/conjugated aromatic group could not be engaged in any of the above-mentioned methods up to now. This represents a major limitation, as unactivated alkenes are produced on a large-scale during petroleum processing and thus represent excellent building blocks for chemical synthesis.^{15,16} The low reactivity towards addition as well as the instability of the resulting intermediates, lacking the stabilizing effect of neighboring group compared to activated systems, has hampered the development of these processes. Our original mechanistic proposal invoked a Ni(o)/Ni(I)/Ni(III) catalytic cycle but intriguingly, could not explain neither the high selectivity observed towards the conjugative cross-coupling (vs. cross coupling Ar-Alk and homocoupling products Ar-Ar). Despite recent advances in the field, mechanistic understanding of Ni-catalyzed processes lies behind methodology developments, likely due to the lability of organonickel species and the multiple mechanistic manifolds potentially underlying these transformations.

Herein, we report an unprecedented intermolecular reductive dicarbofunctionalization applicable to non-directed, unactivated olefins using two electrophilic carbon sources (Scheme 1, bottom). This protocol allows the simultaneous addition of alkyl and aryl groups across non-electronically biased double bonds devoid of a coordinating site at room temperature. We also present an in depth mechanistic investigation involving both experimental and computational results. We demonstrate that, although Ni(o) species might be formed under the reductive conditions, a catalytic cycle involving formally Ni(I)/Ni(III) redox processes is more likely responsible for the observed reactivity. Further, we characterize the individual steps responsible for the high chemoselectivity observed in the reaction and unravel the important role of the organic reductant in these transformations.

Results and Discussion

Optimization

4-Phenyl-1-butene, *p*-iodoanisole and *tert*-butyl iodide were selected as model substrates to find the optimal reaction conditions (Table 1).¹⁷ Initially, a screening of nickel pre-catalysts combined with 4,4'-di-(*tert*-butyl)-2,2'-dipyridyl (**1a**) was performed in dioxane in the presence of TDAE (tetrakis-(dimethylamino)ethylene) as reductant (Table 1, entries 1-5).¹⁸

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions.^a

Entry	Cat (x mol%)	Ligand (y mol%)	Solvent	Yield 1 , (%) ^b
1	Ni(acac) ₂ (10)	L1 (12)	Dioxane	NR
2	NiCl ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	"	48
3	NiCl ₂ (py) ₄ (10)	L1 (12)	"	47
4	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	"	64
5	NiBr ₂ ·diglyme (10)	L1 (12)	"	64
6	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	DME	0
7	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	DMF	0
8	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	THF	29
9	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L1 (12)	Toluene	32
10	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L2 (12)	Dioxane	0
11	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L3 (12)	"	0
12	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L4 (12)	"	33 (19) ^c
13	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L5 (12)	"	39
14	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (10)	L6 (12)	"	0
15	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (5)	L1 (6)	"	64
16 ^d	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (5)	L1 (6)	"	0
17 ^e	NiBr ₂ ·glyme (5)	L1 (6)	"	82 (78) ^f

^a The reaction was carried out with 4-phenyl-1-butene (0.1 mmol), p-iodoanisole (0.2 mmol), tert-butyl iodide (0.2 mmol) in 1 mL of solvent. ^b The yield was determined by ¹H-NMR using mesitylene as internal standard. ^c Recovered 4-phenyl-1-butene. ^d Zn or Mn used as reductant instead of TDAE. ^e p-iodoanisole (0.15 mmol), tert-butyl iodide (0.3 mmol) and TDAE (0.3 mmol) were used. ^f Isolated yield after column chromatography in silica gel.

The results revealed NiBr₂·glyme and NiBr₂·diglyme as the most suitable nickel sources, providing the desired product **1** in 64% yield with exclusive regioselectivity. Using NiBr₂·glyme, different solvents were then tested with significantly different outcomes: while reactions in strong

coordinating solvents such as DME or DMF did not give the desired product (Table 1, entries 6 and 7), those carried out in toluene or THF proceeded smoothly, albeit in lower yields (Table 1, entries 8 and 9). The examination of different bidentate ligands (L2–L6) did not improve the reaction efficiency (Table 1, entries 10–14). On the other hand, we were delighted to observe that the catalyst loading of the system could be reduced to 5 mol % without eroding the reaction efficiency (Table 1, entry 15). We also found that the use of TDAE as reductant is crucial for this transformation. Replacing TDAE with metallic reductants such as Zn or Mn did not deliver the desired product (Table 1, entry 16). Finally, a careful modification of the molar ratio of the components and reagents was performed, resulting in the formation of dicarbofunctionalization adduct **1** in 78% isolated yield as a single regioisomer at room temperature (Table 1, entry 17).

Reaction Scope

With the optimized conditions in hand, we set out to explore the scope of this transformation. First, different aromatic halides were examined. As depicted in Scheme 2, a variety of substituents, both electron-withdrawing (CO₂Me, F, CF₃) and electron-donating (Me, t-Bu, OMe) were well tolerated in para and meta positions so that dicarbofunctionalized products 2–12 could be isolated in good yields. Excellent chemoselectivity was observed in these processes as demonstrated by the lack of reactivity of C(sp²)–Br and C(sp²)–Cl bonds present in compounds 13 and 16, which were obtained in 78% and 66% yield, respectively. More sterically demanding ortho-substituted aryl iodides could also be successfully incorporated, furnishing the desired products in synthetically useful yields (14 and 15). Heterocyclic aromatic iodides containing indole and pyridine moieties were successfully applied in this protocol, furnishing the dicarbofunctionalization products (17, 24, and 25) in good yields. In addition, this transformation provided orthogonal reactivity with respect to classical cross-coupling procedures, as Bpin derivative **18** was successfully obtained in 67% yield, rendering the possibility of subsequent cross-coupling reactions via the C(sp²)–B bond. The process also tolerated a wide variety of sensitive functional groups, such as free N–H or O–H groups, and thus the three-component cross-coupling products could be isolated in synthetically useful yields (20–24).

Scheme 2. Reaction scope on aryl iodide.^a For reaction conditions, see Table 1, entry 17. ^b Aryl iodide (0.1 mmol), and alkene (0.3 mmol) were used under otherwise identical conditions.

To further demonstrate the versatility of this method, different alkenes were tested (Scheme 3). The protocol was applied to a variety of terminal aliphatic olefins, devoid of any directing or coordinating group. To our delight, the isolation of dicarbofunctionalization products 26–32 always proceeded in good yields. Vinyl ethers were also good substrates for the reaction, as shown by benzylic ether 33, which could be isolated in 61% yield. The remarkable selectivity of the reaction was again showcased by the presence of primary C(sp³)-Br and C(sp³)-Cl bonds in the aliphatic chain which remained unreacted as shown by the successful isolation of 34 and 35 in 63% and 81% yields, respectively. Additionally, free hydroxy or carbamate groups did not affect the reaction efficiency, furnishing the desired products 36–38. Ester functionalities were well tolerated (39), including those containing more acidic protons at the α -carbon such as malonate derivatives 40 and 41.

Finally, different tertiary alkyl iodides were also assessed in combination with a diverse set of alkenes and aromatic iodides (Scheme 4). Both cyclic and acyclic alkyl groups as well as keto- and Csp³-Cl containing iodides were well tolerated under the standard reactions conditions, delivering the corresponding cross-alkylation products in moderate to good yields (42–62).

Scheme 3. Reaction scope on alkene (for reaction conditions, see Table 1, entry 17). ^a Aryl iodide (0.1 mmol), and alkene (0.3 mmol) were used under otherwise identical conditions.

Scheme 4. Reaction scope on alkyl iodide (for reaction conditions, see Table 1, entry 17). ^a Alkyl iodide (0.1 mmol), and alkene (0.3 mmol) were used under otherwise identical conditions.

The method could also be applied in the late-stage functionalization of more elaborated alkenes as shown by estrone and amino acid-containing adducts 63 and 64 (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Late stage dicarbofunctionalization of alkenes. For reaction conditions, see Table 1, entry 17. ^a 0.1 mmol of aryl iodide, and 0.3 mmol of alkene were used under otherwise identical conditions.

Aiming to expand the synthetic utility of the method, we set out to apply the optimized protocol to the selective functionalization of diverse polyene and enyne substrates (Scheme 6). Interestingly, 1,6-dienes bearing different tethers could successfully undergo this reductive cascade difunctionalization, accomplishing the simultaneous formation of three new C–C bonds to deliver cyclopentane derivatives 65–67 in good yields and high stereoselectivity (ca. 10:1). Pyrrolidine-containing derivatives 68 and 69 were obtained with similar efficiency but with lower levels of stereocontrol. Internal alkenes are also amenable to the optimized conditions as shown by cyclopentane derivative 70. More challenging substrates, encompassing three different double bonds, also underwent the desired transformation, delivering bicyclic products 71 and 72 with high efficiency considering that four new C–C bonds are forged and a single stereoisomer is obtained in the reactions. Analogously, a 1,9-dien-6-yne delivered the corresponding bicycle 73 in 54% yield as an inseparable 1.5:1 mixture of diastereoisomers. These transformations provide rapid access to molecular complexity from alkenes and showcase the efficiency of the method, as an >80% average yield per bond-forming event can be calculated. Further, the structure of the major isomers obtained in the reactions producing 65 and 72 could be unambiguously determined by X-ray diffraction analysis (Supporting Information) of the corresponding single crystals.¹⁷

We also turned our attention toward the reactivity of 1,3-dienes. These substrates represented an excellent platform to explore the regioselectivity of the reaction, as 1,2-, 1,3-, or 1,4- difunctionalization products could in principle be obtained. Both alkyl- and aryl-substituted 1,3-dienes furnished, selectively, 1,4-dicarbofunctionalization products 74–78 in good yields in ca. 4:1 E:Z ratio (Scheme 6b). Further, 1,4- and 1,5- dienes (i.e., norbornadiene and COD, re-

spectively) could also be successfully engaged in this dicarbofunctionalization reaction, producing the corresponding adducts 79 and 80 in moderate yields (Scheme 6c,d).

Scheme 6. (a) Dicarbofunctionalization of Unactivated 1,n-(Di)-en-yne or Trienes (for the reaction conditions, see Table 1, entry 17). (b) Dicarbofunctionalization of 1,3-Dienes.^a (c, d) Dicarbofunctionalization of 1,4- and 1,5-Dienes^b

^aThe reaction was carried out with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene (0.4 mmol), aryl iodide (0.2 mmol), tert-butyl iodide (0.4 mmol), and TDAE (0.6 mmol) in 2 mL of dioxane except for compound 78 in which 2,3-diphenylbutadiene (0.2 mmol), aryl iodide (0.4 mmol), tert-butyl iodide (0.6 mmol), and TDAE (0.6 mmol) reacted in 2 mL of dioxane.

^bThe reaction was carried out with 4-iodoanisole (0.1 mmol), diene (0.5 mmol), tert-butyl iodide (0.3 mmol), and TDAE (0.3 mmol) in 1 mL of dioxane.

Mechanistic investigations

Control experiments were designed to shed light on the mechanism governing these transformations. Addition of radical scavengers (TEMPO, BHT and 1,1-diphenylethene) completely shut down the reaction.¹⁷ Further, examples summarized in Scheme 6 together with previous experiments utilizing radical clocks,¹⁴ signaled the presence of

C-centered radicals along the reaction pathway. The involvement of secondary alkyl iodides as potential reaction intermediates, produced as a result of a nickel-mediated ATRA process between the olefin and the alkyl halide, could also be ruled out, as neither these species could be detected in the reaction mixtures at any given time nor, when prepared independently, engaged into cross-coupling reactions with the corresponding aryl halides under the standard reaction conditions.

Along control experiments, DFT calculations were performed using propene, *tert*-butyl iodide, iodobenzene and 4,4'-di-*tert*-butyl-2,2'-dipyridine ligand (**L1**) as model structures to gain additional insights onto the reaction mechanism.¹⁷ The computational study focused first on our original mechanistic proposal which invoked Ni(o) species **A**, generated *in situ* under the reductive conditions at the outset of the reaction (Scheme 7a).¹⁴ Such low valent metal species were proposed to undergo oxidative addition onto the ArI moiety to produce ArNi(II)I intermediate **B** (TS_{A-B}, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 11.4$ kcal/mol, Ar = Ph) in a highly exergonic process ($\Delta G = -55.9$ kcal/mol). Addition of an *in situ* generated *tert*-butyl radical **D** onto the unactivated alkene (propene) produced carbon centered radical **E** in an almost thermoneutral process ($\Delta G = -1.3$ kcal/mol) via TS_{D-E} ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5$ kcal/mol). Fast recombination of **E** with aryl nickel(II) complex **B** produces the key Ni(III) intermediate **F** ($\Delta G = 5.1$ kcal/mol) via TS_{B-E} ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 10.1$ kcal/mol). Reductive elimination on **F** produced the corresponding dicarbofunctionalization product **G** and Ni(I)I **C** in a fast, thermodynamically driven process ($\Delta G = -61.8$ kcal/mol) via TS_{F-G} ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 7.2$ kcal/mol). As seen in the left part of Scheme 7a, Ni(I)I species **C**, produced *in situ* in the reaction media after reductive elimination on **F**, were proposed to be responsible for the activation of the alkyl iodide to produce alkyl radical **D** (Alk = *t*Bu). Computationally though, the reaction to produce Ni(II)I₂ species **H** by reaction of Ni(I)I complex **C** with *t*-BuI is a rather uphill process ($\Delta G = 25.1$ kcal/mol) that would be incompatible with a productive reaction outcome at room temperature, thus questioning our original proposal.¹⁴ Still, some of the steps depicted in Scheme 7a could be experimentally validated. For instance, complex **B** seems to be a competent intermediate in the reaction, as shown by the successful transformation of allyl acetate and 4-phenyl-1-butene into the corresponding dicarbofunctionalized products **62** and **4** in the presence of *t*-BuI, TDAE and Ni(II) complex **61** (Scheme 7b).¹⁸

Scheme 7 a-d. a) DFT analysis of our original mechanistic proposal based starting from Ni(o) species. b) Feasibility of **B** to **G**. c) Feasibility of **H** to **B**. d) Comparison of the addition of the *t*-Bu \cdot radical to the free olefin (path a) vs. addition to a Ni^{II} coordinated olefin (path b). Reaction free energies and activation energies (kcal/mol) calculated at UB3LYP/6-31G(d) (C,H,N), LANL2DZ (Ni, I) level in THF (PCM). Ni = (dtbbpy)Ni-I.

Further, the feasibility of reducing Ni(II)I₂ (**H**) species with TDAE and their subsequent transformation into ArNi(II) intermediates **B** in the presence of ArI could be secured by the stoichiometric reaction of Ni(dtbbpy)₂ with TDAE in

the presence of 2-iodotoluene, which cleanly delivered the corresponding ArNi(II) complex **62** as shown in Scheme 7c.

As the nature of the olefinic partner seems to play a key role in these transformations, and alkenes are known to be strong ligands for nickel,¹⁹ their effect on the above-mentioned reaction mechanism was also investigated in detail. In fact, while olefin coordination helps to stabilize Ni(o) species ($\Delta G = -46.3$ kcal/mol for Ni(o)-olefin complex **A'**, see SI), a mechanism involving the addition of alkyl radicals onto the Ni(II)-olefin complex **B'** via TS_{D-F} ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 15.4$ kcal/mol, Scheme 6d, path b) is substantially disfavored compared to the direct addition onto the free olefin ($\Delta G = -1.3$ kcal/mol via TS_{D-E} , $\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5$ kcal/mol) followed by recombination with the $PhNi^{II}$ species **B** to give alkyl Ni(III) complex **F** (Scheme 7d, path a).

In summary, the computational as well as the experimental results depicted in Scheme 7 signal the feasibility of some of the proposed steps along the catalytic cycle (**H** to **B**, **B** to **G**), but raised questions regarding both the specific nature of the nickel intermediates involved in the reaction, and more importantly, their ability to activate the alkyl halide partner. Since Ni(I)I (**C**) does not seem competent in this regard, we set out to interrogate the ability of other nickel species, potentially present in the reaction media, towards the reduction of the C(sp³)-I bond. The results of these investigations have been summarized in Scheme 8. In sharp contrast to **C**, $PhNi(I)$ complex **K** turned out to be a suitable partner for the reduction of the carbon-halogen bond according to DFT calculations ($\Delta G = -0.8$ kcal/mol with $\Delta G^\ddagger = 16.7$ kcal/mol). As in the previous case, coordination to the alkene in **K'** significantly disfavors the desired homolytic cleavage of the carbon-halogen bond ($\Delta G = 8.2$ kcal/mol) (Scheme 8a, top). Other low-valent Ni species were also analyzed in this context. Interestingly, activation of the *tert*-butyl iodide on Ni(o) species **A** resulted in a highly thermodynamically favorable process ($\Delta G = -71.6$ kcal/mol), even when coordination to the olefin is in place **A'** ($\Delta G = -19.6$ kcal/mol) (Scheme 8a, middle).²⁰ In sharp contrast, $PhNi(II)I$ species **B** seem to be much less suited for activation of the alkyl partner, as the reaction is again uphill with $\Delta G = 18.9$ kcal/mol (Scheme 8a, bottom).

Experimental support for these computationally predicted trends is shown in Scheme 8b. The reaction of 1-iodo-1-methylcyclohexane in combination with $NiBr_2 \cdot DME$ and ligand **L1** resulted in no conversion of the alkyl iodide (Scheme 8b, column 1). A similar result was obtained for a reaction with complex **61** in the absence of TDAE (column 2). In contrast, activation of the Csp³-I bond occurs when aryl nickel(II) complex **61** is combined with TDAE (column

3) as well as with Ni(o) complexes ($Ni(COD)_2$) in the presence of **L1** (column 4).

(a) Activation of *t*BuI by different Ni species: DFT calculations

(b) Activation of Alk-I by different Ni species: experimental results

Time (min)	% consumption of Alkyl-I ^a			
	$[Ni(II)I] (1.0 \text{ eq.})$ L1	ArNi(II)Cl (1 eq.) ^b	ArNi(II)Cl (1 eq.) TDAE (1 eq.) ^b	$[Ni(0)] (1.0 \text{ eq.})$ L1
10	0	0	3	-
20	0	0	7	-
30	0	0	20	17
40	no conv.	0	25	-
50	0	0	30	-
60	0	5	33	82
70	0	10	40	-

^aMonitored by GC-MS with dodecane as IS. ^bSolvent: CH₂Cl₂, c⁻: not determined

(c) TDAE as a reductant for Ni(II) and Ni(III) species

Scheme 8 a-c. DFT analysis (a) and experimental results (b) on the reduction of *t*Bu-I in the presence of different Ni species. (c) Computational study on TDAE as a reductant for putative Ni(II) and Ni(III) species present in the reaction media. Reaction free energies and activation energies (kcal/mol) calculated at UB₃LYP/6-31G(d) (C,H,N), LANL2DZ (Ni, I) level in THF (PCM). Ni = (dttbpy)Ni

The facile reduction of *t*Bu-I with Ni(o) to give Ni(I)I complex **C** ($\Delta G = -71.6$ kcal/mol, Scheme 8a, middle), as well as the facile reduction of a Ni(II)I₂ precatalyst to Ni(I)I species with TDAE (**H** to **C**, $\Delta G = -28.8$ kcal/mol in Scheme 8c, left) prompted us to investigate a reaction mechanism in which these species would be involved on the outset of the reaction (Scheme 9). The oxidative addition of **C** onto iodobenzene to produce $PhNi(III)I_2$ **J** turned out to be an endothermic process ($\Delta G = 15.7$ Kcal/mol) but with a moderate activation energy ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 20.4$ kcal/mol). Subsequent

reduction with TDAE to PhNi(I)I **K** is overall thermodynamically favorable ($\Delta G = -25.5$ kcal/mol). Interestingly, the first reduction potential calculated for TDAE suggests its preferential application as a one-electron donor whereas the second reduction seems to be much more demanding, which might explain the need to use the reductant in excess for the reaction (Scheme 8c, right). While activation of *t*Bu-I with Ni(I)I **C** is not thermodynamically favored ($\Delta G = 25.1$ kcal/mol, see Schemes 7a and Scheme 8a, top), PhNi(I) species **K** offered a much more amenable barrier for this process ($\Delta G = -0.8$ kcal/mol via TS_{K-B} with $\Delta G^\ddagger = 16.7$ kcal/mol).^{21,22} The most favorable pathway thereafter intersects with that computed in Scheme 7a and involves the addition of the *t*Bu radical onto the olefin in an off-cycle process to form **E** ($\Delta G = -1.3$ kcal/mol via TS_{D-E} $\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5$ kcal/mol), which undergoes fast recombination with **B** to give Ni(III) intermediate **F** ($\Delta G = 5.1$ kcal/mol via TS_{B-E} $\Delta G^\ddagger = 10.1$ kcal/mol). Reductive elimination delivers product **G** together with Ni(I)I **C** closing the catalytic cycle ($\Delta G = -61.8$ kcal/mol via TS_{F-G} $\Delta G^\ddagger = 7.2$ kcal/mol) (See SI for a comprehensive study of alternative catalytic cycles).¹⁷

Scheme 8. DFT analysis of a Ni(I)-based mechanistic proposal based on. Reaction free energies and activation energies (kcal/mol) calculated at UB₃LYP/6-31G(d) (C,H,N), LANL2DZ (Ni, I) level in THF (PCM). Ni = (dtbbpy)Ni

The mechanism depicted in Scheme 9 is compatible with both computational and experimental results. Further, the significant energy barrier determined for the addition of the electron-rich tertiary alkyl radical **D** to propene (TS_{D-E} $\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5$ kcal/mol) is in line with the existing literature evidence²³ and thus can help to rationalize the difficulties encountered thus far in the dicarbofunctionalization of unactivated olefins. However, despite this good correlation between calculations and experimental evidence, three

features of the reaction, namely the need for an organic reductant (TDAE), and the high chemoselectivity preventing both homocoupling (Alk–Alk, Ar–Ar) or direct heterocoupling (Alk–Ar) products, remained unanswered within the above-mentioned mechanistic picture.

First, the nature of the reductant seemed to play a crucial role for a successful reaction outcome.²⁴ During the optimization campaign, no dicarbofunctionalization products were observed when TDAE was replaced by Zn or Mn which are well established reductants for previously developed reductive couplings (see Table S1 in the SI).^{13,16} As shown in Scheme 10a, and in analogy to the results obtained for TDAE (Scheme 7c), Zn managed to reduce ArNi(II)X species in stoichiometric fashion and, in the presence of *o*-iodotoluene, delivered the corresponding ArNi(II)I complex **83** together with small amounts of arene homocoupling products. However, and in striking contrast to the clean reaction observed with TDAE, when Zn(o) was used as reductant under the standard catalytic conditions, no desired dicarbofunctionalization product **42** was observed (Scheme 10b). Rather, complex mixtures were detected, which signaled that potential organozinc intermediates formed in the reaction media impact the reaction outcome promoting undesired side reactions.^{13,16}

Scheme 9. Control experiments on selectivity with Zn based reductants. For part b, recovered starting materials were quantified with dodecane as internal standard.

Along these lines, we aimed to clarify the origin of the exquisite chemoselectivity observed in these transformations as neither homocoupling (Alk–Alk, Ar–Ar) nor heterocoupling products (Alk–Ar) could be detected in most of the reactions performed with TDAE. As shown in Scheme 11a (path a), activation of *t*Bu-I with PhNi(I) complex **K** is feasible ($\Delta G = -0.8$ kcal/mol via TS_{K-B} with $\Delta G^\ddagger = 16.7$ kcal/mol). Interestingly, a competitive oxidative addition onto PhI to give Ph₂Ni(III)I intermediate **L**, although thermodynamically more likely ($\Delta G = -8.3$ kcal/mol) would require a substantially higher activation energy via TS_{K-L} ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 24.4$ kcal/mol) (Scheme 11a, path b). These results

explain the lack of Ar-Ar homocoupling products in these transformations (which would stem from a facile reductive elimination in **L**) and thus the observed selectivity towards a conjugative cross-coupling involving both electrophiles and the alkene.²⁵ Further, the lack of Alk-Ar direct coupling products under the reaction conditions seems to rule out the participation of ArAlkNi(III)I intermediates.²⁶ As seen in Scheme 10b, the direct recombination of tertiary alkyl radicals **D** with intermediate PhNi(II)I **B** to give **M** is much less favorable ($\Delta G = 9.5$ kcal/mol via TS_{B-M} with $\Delta G^\ddagger = 17.1$ kcal/mol) than the recombination of **B** with C-centered radical **E** to produce the conjugative cross-coupling Ni(III) intermediate **F** ($\Delta G = 5.1$ kcal/mol via TS_{B-F} with $\Delta G^\ddagger = 10.1$ kcal/mol).¹⁷

Scheme 10. (a) Selectivity of PhNi(I) **K**, towards C-I bonds. (b) Selectivity of alkyl radicals for PhNi(II)I complex **B**. Reaction free energies and activation energies (kcal/mol) calculated at UB3LYP/6-31G(d) (C,H,N), LANL2DZ (Ni, I) level in THF (PCM). Ni = (dtbbpy)Ni

CONCLUSIONS

Here, we report the intermolecular dicarbofunctionalization of unactivated alkenes by direct formation of C(sp³)-C(sp³) and C(sp³)-C(sp²) bonds across a variety of unbiased π -systems using two different electrophiles. The reaction, devoid of directing groups or strong electronic

bias on the alkene partner, occurs with exquisite selectivity under mild reaction conditions. The method relies on the combination of a Ni catalyst with TDAE as an organic sacrificial reductant. Both experimental and computational results favor the idea of Ni(I), Ni(II), and Ni(III) species over the original proposal invoking Ni(0) intermediates at the outset of the reaction. Further, our results showcase the different ability of Ni(I) species (Ni(I)I vs PhNi(I)) to reduce the C(sp³)-I bond. The role of the reductant has also been investigated in depth, demonstrating that TDAE-mediated one-electron reductions to form Ni(I) species are highly favorable processes. Further, our results shed light on the reason behind the high chemoselectivity observed in these transformations toward conjugative cross-coupling products. Both the preferential activation of the *t*Bu-I with PhNi(I) over a competitive oxidative addition onto the PhI to give Ph₂Ni(III)I intermediate explain the lack of Ar-Ar homocoupling products. Further, the fact that direct coupling products (Alk-Ar) were not observed under the reaction conditions seems to rule out the participation of ArAlkNi(III)I intermediates in these transformations. We believe our results might have a significant impact in other related reductive coupling reactions as well as in the development of new reactions to harvest alkenes as building blocks for the generation of structural complexity in a highly selective manner utilizing Ni catalysis.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Supplementary information including compound synthesis, characterization, additional experiments and DFT calculations. This material is available free of charge via the Internet

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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■ Reductive dicarbofunctionalizations of non-directed, unactivated alkenes

- No coordinating group
 - Unactivated alkenes
 - Diene and enyne substrates
 - Broad scope & FG tolerance
 - >50 Examples
 - Mechanistic investigations
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